

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

National human resource planning in Bangladesh: An analysis from development perspective

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International Journal of Science and Research Archive, 2025, 14(02), 333-347

Publication history: Received on 02 January 2025; revised on 04 February 2025; accepted on 07 February 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2025.14.2.0424>

Abstract

Human Resource Planning (HRP) first evolved in private sector to ensure efficiency, economy and effectiveness for profit maximization. But in the public sector, it is quite different due to the wider role and responsibilities of the government. The present paper makes an attempt to examine the state of human resource planning in Bangladesh and explore the pattern of relationship among birth, education, employment, and rehabilitation of the population in society. The issue of human resource planning remains un-emphasized in the population policy papers. In the Five-Year Development Plans Bangladesh expresses its repeated emphasis on human resource development and commits to ensure education for all and concentrates on job-centered and technical education but without any human resource planning framework. Its reflection is found, in accelerated growth of higher education devoid of productive employment, massive unemployment including educated youth and in rural urban as well as overseas migration and vulnerability of elderly people. The study reveals a paradoxical relationship among birth, education, employment and re-assimilation of population in Bangladesh and the cycle of events constituted by them is seriously disrupted that appear as the most potential threats to development.

Keywords: Human Resource Planning; Development; Population Planning; Education Planning; Employment Planning; Elderly Support Planning

1. Introduction

Population not only constitutes the primary goal of development, but also acts as the basic resources and driving forces in the development process (Alexandratos, 2005). The role of population in the development process depends primarily on proper national human resource planning (NHRP) formulated concomitantly with the overall development planning of the country concerned. Human resource planning is not a new phenomenon; it has been in the practice in private sector as the core element of Human Resource Management (HRM) for a long period and plays important role in ensuring efficiency, economy and effectiveness [3Es] in employee's performance and thereby maximizing profit (Chakraborty et al., 2004). Governments in developing countries need national human resource planning to carry out their responsibilities and achieving the national goal of development. In the absence of a comprehensive approach to National Human Resource Planning (NHRP), their development efforts encounter unmanageable hazards and vulnerabilities (S. Mann, 2014; S. C. Mann & Islam, 2015). They have different development plans, enormous external supports in the form of aids, loan and expert knowledge, and remarkable institutional deployment; in spite of all these cannot pull them out of the vicious cycle of underdevelopment and overthrow the same. In this context, the present paper makes an attempt to develop a conceptual framework for national level human resources planning (NHRP) and to analyze realities related to population and development in Bangladesh using the framework developed on the basis of data and information available in authentic secondary sources.

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1.1. Development Population Interface and Need for Planning

Population plays the most vital role in the whole gamut of development, both in steering the process and in justifying the end of the process. From the perspective of any republican policy, this role can be phrased as 'development of the people, by the people and for the people' (Brown, 1985). For undesirable socio-political and economic dynamics, development may not be directed for the benefit of the people but without the labor of people, mental, intellectual, and physical (Glick, 1995), the goal of development, whatever it be, cannot be achieved (Brennan, 2009; Lee et al., 2017). The 'world population patterns and trends, population growth dynamics, and sustainable development' has led to a 'new understanding' of population and development (UNESCO 2019). This new understanding unveils the interactive and interdependent pattern of relationship between population and development not only from the perspective of a particular country, from the global perspective. 'This new understanding' is the result of six major international conferences convened by the United Nations during the 1990s' (United Nations Conference on Environment and Development – Rio de Janeiro, 1992, International Conference on Population and Development – Cairo, 1994, The World Summit for Social Development – Copenhagen, 1995, Fourth World Conference on Women – Beijing, 1995, United Nations Conference on Human Settlements (Habitat II) – Istanbul, 1996 and World Food Summit – Rome, 1996) and the five elements that make up this understanding place population in the broad perspectives of development, environment, gender, and human rights. It is revealed in the understanding that the post-colonial emphasis on 'over population' as a causal factor of underdevelopment is identified misguided and concomitantly the past family planning campaign was too narrow (Patterson & Shrestha 1988, Harshe, 1995). It also discerns that 'population, consumption, and environment are inextricably interlinked', women need prominence in social development and the rights of generations (UNFA, 1997, pp. 1-7). All of this in the final analysis uphold the reality of the population centrism of development process and identify the 'means and end' positions population in all development moves in the developing countries.

In a country, designated as a People's Republic, from a political perspective, people are the real owner of the state and have the right to play a role at any phase of the development policy making and policy implementation cycle (Gertston, 2014). Secondly, social stability, one of the basic preconditions for development efforts, depends primarily on the population of the society, pattern of relationships, production relation, human relation and ecological relations existing among the population concerned (Midgley, 1995). Population must first be addressed in view of creating dynamic equilibrium in the society. Finally, population is the energy or fuel to drive the engine of development and their labor is converted to resources (Ayres & Warr, 2009). The success or failure of the development governance of a country is substantively based on its ability to manage and utilize its population regardless of its age, gender, education, profession, and location of residence, rural or urban.

How and in which fields/areas population will play the developmental role it always depends on the population or human resource planning of the government and the government's ability to integrate population with the development plan and efforts side by side with its governance system. However, in the array of all these functions, human resource planning that complies with the development goal(s) of the country deserves careful attention with seriousness and expertise.

1.2. National Human Resource Planning: A Conceptual Framework

Human Resource Planning [HRP] occupies a central position in Human Resource Management (HRM), by which management determines its future human resources and how existing human resources can be used effectively and efficiently for goal attainment. It aims to have the right number and the right kind of employees, at the right place at the right time, performing actions which result in long-term benefits for both the individual and the organization (Jackson and Schuler 1990, pp. 223-239). HRP analyzes the human resource needs of the organization under changing conditions and develops the activities required to satisfy these needs. It is of great importance at the advent of industrial humanism as a reaction to the pro-worker socialist philosophy, competitive market forces, globalization, technological innovation and information revolution. Human Resource Planning (HRP) is a very complex process consisting of four major stages including (i) Analysis of Existing Resources based on certain characteristics which are relevant for planning purposes, (ii) HR Demand Forecasting, analysis of the staffing requirements necessary for the organization to succeed in achieving its business objectives, (iii) HR Supply Forecasting to anticipate changes in the supply of labor by taking into account of anticipated losses from the existing workforce and the external supply of suitable staff from external sources outside, and lastly (iv) formulation of Human resource Plan based on information obtained from the first three stages.

HRP has two inseparable dimensions: hard human resource planning and soft human resource planning. Hard HRP stresses on rationalizing individual performance in the organization. Soft HRP emphasizes individuals and their self-direction and places commitment, trust, and self-regulated behavior at the center of any strategic approach to people. Both hard and soft HRP is essential for comprehensive HRP in the organization.

1.2.1. Context of National Human Resource Planning

The human resource planning process originated and practiced in the private sector follows a micro-level organizational perspective. Its main focus is the interest of the organization, i.e. organizational profitability. Public sector organizations also follow the same approach to HRP to achieve the organizational goal. The market-based approach to public administration configured in the New Public Management (NPM) paradigm views the citizen as a customer (Rosenbloom,1986) and engages in business and commercial activities needed for the development of the country and also works with business organizations (Self,1993). The Public Private Partnership (PPP) is a recent example of this approach (Savas, 1987). It is practically difficult for any functional-level public enterprise to directly involve in HRP beyond its organizational jurisdiction. It can only follow the government's human resource employment policy framework without jeopardizing its own organizational goal. The issue of national development and the consideration of the population of the country remain outside its jurisdiction. In such a situation, only government can prepare the HRP at national level including the total population of the countries using the central level ministries. It is also an inseparable part of its development move, legal obligation, and political agenda. But to do this essential and complicated function, government firstly needs a strategic framework of HRP, which is obviously different from the micro-level organization perspective, and requires special institutional arrangement to prepare national level human resource planning (NHRP) a holistic societal perspective.

Development governance comprises two broad and mutually interdependent functions, firstly to maintain dynamic equilibrium in the society and secondly to ensure development by involving its population. NHRP encompasses the whole country as its organization, people are its owner, and government is responsible for making HRP including all the people and institutions therein. NHRP planning includes all issues related to its population size, education, employment, and elderly care in a very coherent manner.

1.2.2. Basic elements in the national human resource planning process

Development is a holistic phenomenon that requires holistic planning in general and holistic HRP for the role and position of population in the development process. Complying with the broader objectives of development governance comprising discipline, development, and peace, National Human Resource Planning (NHRP) primarily requires dynamic equilibrium in the society. It is ascertained through harmonious balance in population growth, education, employment, and proper supports in post productive life. Dynamic equilibrium acts as the basic premise or foundation of NHRP system and integrates population planning, education planning, employment planning and elderly planning as its four inseparable subsystems with specific role. The most functional role of development governance for dynamic equilibrium is to ensure the uninterrupted continuity of the cycle of these four events shown in the following figure.

Figure 1 System of National Human Resource Planning

These subsystems have their own constituent elements. Balanced internal relationship of the constituent elements of a subsystem and inter-relationships among the subsystems together act as the precondition for ensuring dynamic equilibrium in the society. NHRP thus has to deal with these issues integrated way, with caution, and in a calculative manner. Both the hard and the soft dimensions mentioned earlier need to be properly incorporate in all phases of NHRP.

1.2.3. National HRP Process

The national HRP system requires a comprehensive process and an integrated instructional arrangement involving different ministries/institutions under the supreme national authority to run the process. The process by giving due emphasis on the hard and soft sides of human resource planning and basing on the strategic cycle of events needs:

- To analyze the existing demographic characteristics of country's population.
- To identify and evaluate the employment opportunities that is demand for man power in different sectors the within and outside the country
- To assesses the current position of human resources of the country in the context of existing the employment scope
- To explore the gap between the demand of manpower and the existing strength of the country to avail the opportunities
- To take necessary policy decisions on the existing population pyramid and focuses of current education and human development program and strategies regarding the aging population
- To formulate NHRP properly addressing the dynamic equilibrium in the strategic cycle of population, education, employment and retirement and
- To forecast the National Human Resource Plan for action.

The context and the basic elements of NHRP configures a distinct societal approach which is holistic nature and substantively different from micro level organizational approach to HRP. It is to mention here that when the government proceeds with NHRP it accounts the realities concerned with human resources in any organization to make a calculation of demand and supply sides and particular situation provides guidelines too.

1.3. Human Resource Planning in Bangladesh

The different elements of NHRP briefly highlighted in the previous sections have been elaborated in this section to analyze the pattern or status of NHRP in Bangladesh. The dynamic equilibrium through the strategic cycle of events and the hard and soft dimensions of planning are discussed together.

1.3.1. Population Planning

Population planning accompanies some of the demographic characteristics of a country including fertility rate, population size, gender, age, and other issues (Dasgupta, 1995, Ezeh et al., 2012). The pattern of relationship among these issues determines the internal balance of the population of the country. The nature of internal balance primarily reflected in the population pyramid of the country that exposes three types of population growth (i) rapidly growing population is indicated by broad base, (ii) stable population represents narrow base, and (iii) declining population is evident from very thin base, and large chest refers to a prospective population structure having much productive capability. The population pyramid has a direct relationship with development. The size of the population reflected in the pyramid is directly proportional to the development continuum of the country. The nature of the pyramid reflects different dependency ratios such as *total dependency ratio*, *youth dependency ratio*, *elderly dependency ratio* and potential support ratio from quantitative perspective, the hard dimensions of population planning (Vishnevsky & Shcherbakova, 2018). Development, in fact, is the result of the forces of total dependency ratio and potential support ratio. The demographic dividend appears in the population pyramid. Quantitative strength is not enough unless it is supported by the soft dimension of population planning. The soft population planning starts with governance perception about population, whether population is burden or resource, and takes into account cultural dimension, gender, and interpersonal relationship in addition to world view of population.

Planning the growth of population and sociocultural bonds of population depends on the perception level and visionary position of national governance headed by political authority (Friedmann, 2005). How the authority views population, whether as burden or productive assets, molds the conceptual framework of population planning, and this framework has profound influence on the entire system of NHRP.

The constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh that recognizes people as owners of the country endows them with supreme dignity and authority. Constitutional provisions for sustaining fundamental rights, ensuring the supply of basic needs, and providing employment opportunities legally bound the government to involve in human resource planning. Government begins to deal with these issues through its population policy. All the population policies including the last one enacted in 2012 do not pay attention to national human resource planning (Islam, 2012). Considering population as a burden, it focuses mainly on family planning with the core objective of reducing the size of population and program activities are also designed accordingly. The government has implemented a family planning

program and has made all efforts to reduce population through birth control measures since the 1970s (El-Saharty, Zunaid-Ahsan & May, 2014), consequently, the fertility rate came down from 6.92 in 1970 to 2.19 in 2018 which is quite evident from the following Figure;

Figure 2 Population trend in Bangladesh

Despite this result Bangladesh ranks eighth largest country in the world in terms of population, but territorially it is a very small country where more than 166 million people live in a territory of 130,170 km² only and 1278 people live in per square kilometer of land (Fardoush, 2018). The following table depicts the picture the status of population of Bangladesh in terms of age and gender.

Table 1 Population of Bangladesh (in millions)

Age group	Total	Percentage (%)	Male	Female
0-14	52.3	32.4	26.9	25.4
15-24	27.4	17.0	13.6	13.9
25-34	26.1	16.2	11.8	14.3
35-44	21.3	13.2	10.5	10.8
45-54	15.8	9.8	8.0	7.8
55-64	10.5	6.5	5.7	4.8
65+	7.9	4.9	4.6	3.3
Total Population	161.3	100	81.0	80.3

Source: Labor Force Survey 2016-2017

The population pyramid of Bangladesh exposes the population fact that the trend is positive in nature but still the size of the productive forces is not satisfactory compared to the size of the total population.

Figure 3 The population pyramid of Bangladesh

The demographic dividend is quite absent in the present population of Bangladesh, which is necessary to evolve the population as a resource and forces for the development of the country. For creating a demographic dividend the present perspective of the population policy need to be changed, a shift is needed from population burden perspective to population resource perspective.

From the analysis of the dependency and potential support ratio the picture revealed is not congenial for the development of the country. The total dependency ratio, the ratio of combined youth population (ages 0-14) and elderly population (ages 65+) per 100 people of working age (ages 15-64). (Kabir et al, 2016). A high total dependency ratio indicates that the working-age population and the overall economy face a greater burden to support and provide social services for young and elderly persons, who are often economically dependent.

In 2015, the total dependency ratio (0-14 and 65+ per 15-64) for Bangladesh was a 52.6 ratio. The total dependency ratio (0-14 and 65+ per 15-64) of Bangladesh fell gradually from 91 ratio in 1970 to 52.6 ratio in 2015 (Kabir et al, 2016). Despite the statistically declining trend, the total dependency ratio does too high and is not support development. In addition, the elderly dependency ratio is too high which will be discussed in the following section.

1.4. Education Planning

Education planning is central to NHRP due to its role in processing the population as human resources and effective forces of production and development change in country. It determines the objective of education and sets strategies, policies, procedures, program, and standards to achieve objectives (Rahman, 2015). Education planning aims to 'ensuring the efficient delivery of sustainable and quality education throughout the education system, from preschool to tertiary-level institutions (Roy, et al, 2020). For NHRP education planning must take into account two issues: total populations of the country and current and future employment scope for the population. Education planning also has both hard and soft dimensions. The hard dimension includes establishing a proper link among the different levels of education and generation of professional or occupational skills among the students which will be helpful for them to comfortably involve themselves in the production of food and thereby contribute to the national economic development. The soft education dimension is necessary for them visionary persons with normative qualities endowed with cultural alignment and commitment. A wider chest population pyramid is not enough for the development of the country; the population should be trained in a planned manner keeping their individual goals, social goal, and national goal ahead.

In Bangladesh, there are relentless efforts on the part of the government to shape the education system of the country and four education commissions/committees reports and two full-fledged education policies (Bangladesh Education Commission Report, May, 1974, Interim Education Policy 1978, New Education Policy 1978, Mozid Khan Education Committee Report 1983, Dr. Shamshul Haq Education Commission Report 2000, National Education Policy (draft) 1999, Mian Education

Commission Report 2003, Mian Education Commission Report 2003, National Education Policy (draft) 2009, National Education Policy 2010) have been produced to structure the education system. In addition, the draft education law entitled 'Education Act, 2016' has also been endorsed by the Cabinet and published on April 8 for public comments. (Choudhury & Rahman, 2015). However, most of the promises and aspirations of those policies never came into fruition (<https://futrlaw.org/the-education-act-2016-a-critical-analysis>). Given the circumstances with the different commission reports and education policies, the present paper concentrates on the prevailing realities in the education sector and tries to discern their relevance with HRP and development of the country.

There are different types of education programs run by different institutions and having conflicting relationship with each other exposes the basic weakness of the education system in the country. The enrollment of students and the nature of educations at the undergraduate and graduate levels expose the anomalies in the education program and the gap between the demand / necessity for development and education in the country.

Enrollment and dropout of Students: The Bangladesh government conducts universal primary education for all, which is reflected in the net enrollment trend in the primary education (Table 1). The present net enrolment is 97.97% while it was 87.2% in 2005. It can be considered satisfactory. But the high dropout rate at primary, secondary and higher secondary levels blur this high rate of enrollment at entry level.

Table 2 Enrollment Rate in Primary Education, 2005-2016

Year	Net Enrolment Rate (%)		
	Boys	Girls	Total
2005	84.6	90.1	87.2
2006	87.6	94.5	90.9
2007	87.8	94.7	91.1
2008	87.9	90.4	90.8
2009	89.1	99.1	93.9
2010	92.2	97.6	94.8
2011	92.7	97.3	94.9
2012	95.4	98.1	96.7
2013	96.2	98.4	97.3
2014	96.6	98.8	97.7
2015	97.1	98.8	97.7
2016	97.01	98.8	97.96

Source: Bangladesh Education Statistics 2016

Currently 19.2 % of students are dropped out at the primary level. The dropout rate is highest at the secondary level (38.30%), while it is 20.08% it in higher secondary education. From a development perspective this is an alarming picture. This indicates the gap between population and education in addition to the disrupted nature of education. Among this, the positive sign is that the dropout rate at all three levels is in decreasing trend since 2008 (Table-2).

Table 3 Year-wise dropout rate (%) in Primary, Secondary and Higher Secondary Level (Boys and Girls Together) 2008-2016

Year	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Primary	49.3	45.1	39.8	29.7	26.2	21.4	20.9	20.4	19.2
Secondary	61.38	55.31	55.26	53.28	44.65	43.18	41.59	40.29	38.30
Higher Secondary	46.86	42.11	37.36	37.13	21.80	21.60	21.37	20.70	20.08

1.4.1. Education at the undergraduate and graduate levels

Higher education is offered by a number of normal public universities by private universities in Bangladesh. According to the 2016 statistics there are 36 public and 95 private universities in the country any they offer undergraduate and graduate level education programs in different discipline. About 3.15 million students are enrolled in these universities. Private universities have only about 10% of the total of students. Among all the universities in Bangladesh, the National University occupies special positions due to its nature and number of students who are attached to it through different attached colleges. Established in 1992, the National University has 249 colleges / institutions (Government 275, Non-Government 1974; Honors 770+, Masters [both preliminary and final] 145; Women 123) affiliated with it. The highest number of students, approximately 73% of public university students pursue their degree program in these affiliated institutions. Generally, those who do not have scope to get enrolled in other public universities continue their studies under the national university, though the overall quality of education is very often questioned from different corners.

The following table shows the number and percentage of students in different universities.

Table 4 Total number of university students

University		No. of universities	No. of students	Percentage
Public	Conventional Public Universities	34	264084	8.36
	National University	1	2300053	72.84
	Open University	1	256304	8.12
Private Universities		95	337157	10.68
Total		131	3157598	100

Source: UGC Annual Report 2016

The higher education program in Bangladesh hardly corresponds to the productive employment and development capabilities which are reflected in the information presented in the following tables. Practically, Science, Agriculture, Medical and Technical education have more employment opportunities and such education can also play vital role in the development process of the country. Among all university students only 12.5% receive technical education while 33.1% study arts and humanities and 27.8% are social science students. Arts, Humanities, and social science students constitute 60.9% of the total students, who have hardly any opportunity to engage them in any productive employment in line with their educations in the university. Recently there has been an upward trend in business education both in public (24.5%) and private (33.38%) universities, though business graduates do not have employment scope compatible with their education and degree.

Table 5 Percentage of students based on Subjects in Public Universities

Subjects	University						Total	
	34 Public Universities		National University		Open University		No. of students	Percentage
	No. of students	Percentage	No. of students		No. of students	Percentage		
Arts and Humanities	42472	16.1	668824	29.1	222393	86.8	933689	33.1
Social Science	37928	14.4	745025	32.4	0	0.0	782953	27.8
Science, Agriculture, Medical and Technical	127024	48.1	215441	9.4	10648	4.2	353113	12.5
Business	35161	13.3	650608	28.3	5194	2.0	690963	24.5
Education	3036	1.1	512	0.0	14277	5.6	17825	0.6
Law	5337	2.0	14819	0.6	750	0.3	20906	0.7
Diploma/Certificate and others	13126	5.0	4824	0.2	3042	1.2	20992	0.7
Total	264084		2300053		256304		2820441	

Source: University Grant Commission (UGC).

The numbers of students in private universities are very low compared to the number of private universities that share only 10% of the total of university students. But the inspiring picture is that 48.38% of the total private university students are studying science, agriculture, and Medical and Technical/Engineering which represents about 28% of the students of the country studying these subjects.

Table 6 Percentage of Students Based on Subjects in Private Universities (2016)

Subjects	Total	
	No. of students	Percentage
Arts, Humanities, Social Science, Education and Law	75448	22.38
Science, Agriculture, Medical, and Technical/Engineering	136133	40.38
Business	112553	33.38
Pharmacy	10343	3.07
Diploma/Certificate and others	2680	0.79
Total	337157	

Source: University Grant Commission (UGC).

The realities in the education sector highlight the crude fact that the entire education program in Bangladesh is not based on the vision and mission vision suitable for equipping population as human resources. It cannot be said that education in the country is based on any plan; rather, it is directionless in nature and thus creating educated unemployment in the country.

1.4.2. Employment Planning

Employment planning, which essentially represents HRP in private sector organizations and is necessary to have an accurate estimate of the number of employees required, with matching skill for the organization. Assesses human resource needs at the different levels of organization and forecasts the designs recruitment, promotion, and development plan. The national human resource planning carried out by the central authority of the country is quite different from it. NHRP assumes the responsibility for facilitating and ensuring the employment of the country. It requires:

- To scan the present and future within the plan period employment scope within the country in both public and private and also outside the country.
- Assess the nature of expertise required to exploit the available employment opportunity.
- To design a plan to process the population through an education and training program.
- To develop strategies and institutional support to ensure the of the people in the respective fields of employment

Human resources play a vital role in the economy of Bangladesh. Out of total population of 161.3 million, the working age population is about 109 million and of them only 63.5 million is identified as the labor force while 45.55 million of the working age population are not found in the labor force (Table-6). What these remaining working age population is doing is the point of serious analysis. A portion of them are students pursuing their education in different educational institutions, and the other is unemployed. The total number of students at the higher secondary to master levels in different educational institutions during the same period is about 8 million (Table 7). If this number is deduced then 37.55 million people are unemployed. In the labor force statistics only 2.7 million people of the 63.5 million labor force are shown unemployed (Table -8). Unemployed people therefore are more than 40 millions.

Table 7 Working-age Population (in '000)

	Total	Male	Female
Total Working Age Population	109054 (109.0)	54080 (54.08)	54974 (54.97)
Labor Force	63504 (63.50)	43528 (43.52)	19976 (19.97)
Not in Labor Force	45549 (45.54)	10551 (10.55)	34998 (34.99)

Source: Labor Force Survey 2016-201

Table 8 Total number of students at different levels of education

Sl.No	Levels of Education	Total Students
1	Primary	19067761
2	Secondary	9743072
3	Higher Secondary	3678890
4	University & others	4312494
	Total	36802187

Table 9 Population and Employment Statistics, 2016

	Total	Male	Female
Population (Million)	161.3	81.0	80.3
Total working age population (In '000)	109054	54080	54974
Labor force in Bangladesh (In '000)	63504	43528	19976
Not in labor force (In '000)	45549	10551	34998
Employed	60828	42182	18646
Unemployed (In Millions)	2676000/2.7	1.3	1.4

Source: Labor Force Survey 2016-2017

The nature of employment reveals an alarming picture between education and employment. Agriculture is the highest employer in the country, second is the service sector and third is the industrial sector (Table 9). Highly educated manpower is not employed in agriculture sector generally those who have not completed secondary level education are engaged in agricultural activities. The service sector includes government service and private service employees. The number of people in overseas is counted in the service sector. In the service sector, there are high-ranking functionaries as well as the lower-level employees. Out of 23.7 million people in the service sector, more than 10 millions are overseas wage earners. This sector also could not accommodate a higher number of educated people. In the industrial sector, maximum employees are at worker level and few are in the higher managerial position. The analysis of employment situation in the three different sectors explores the fact that there is a huge number of educated unemployed people in the country.

Table 10 Employed population aged 15 or older, by economic sector, sex, and area (in '000')

Sector of Employment	Total	Male	Female
Agriculture	24693	13565	11128
Industry	12424	9279	3145
Service	23711	19338	4372
Total	60828	42182	18646

Source: Statistical Yearbook 2017

The most alarming situation is that quite a large number of Indians work in the managerial posts in the industrial and commercial sectors of Bangladesh. As a result, Bangladesh becomes the fourth largest remittance source for India. India remits \$10b in 2017 from Bangladesh and at least 1.0 m Indians work in Bangladesh (<http://www.dailyindustry.news/bangladesh-becomes-4th-largest-remittance-source-india/>). Although there are educated unemployed people in Bangladesh, their education does not fit with the requirements of those position. This situation reflects a devastating weakness in education and employment planning in Bangladesh. However, with all the weaknesses, the main power is still the vital force for the development of the country, which is quite clear from the remittance earning of the country.

Table 11 Remittance flow in Bangladesh

Financial Year	No. Of Expatriate Worker (Thousand)	Amount of Remittance (Million \$)	Growth (%)
2007-2008	875	7914.78	32.39
2008-2009	475	9689.16	22.42
2009-2010	427	10987.4	13.40
2010-2011	439	11650.32	6.03
2011-2012	691	12843.4	10.24
2012-2013	441	14461.15	12.60
2013-2014	409	14228.3	-1.16
2014-2015	461	15316.91	7.70
2015-2016	685	14931.00	-2.52
2016-2017	905	12769.45	-14.48

Source: Bangladesh Economic Review -2018 (BBS)

The realities in Bangladesh in terms of remittance earning and remittance giving to India provide a serious point to formulate its NHRP. Bangladesh alone earned 12.8 billion US\$ whereas 10 billion US\$ were remitted to India only in 2017

1.5. Elderly Dependency Planning

Elderly dependency planning is very much related to *elderly dependency ratio* and potential support ration .Elderly dependency ratio is the ratio of the elderly population (65 +) per 100 people of working age (ages 15-64) while the potential support ratio is the number of working-age people (ages 15-64) per one elderly person (ages 65+) (<https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-factbook/>). Increases in the elderly dependency ratio put added pressure on government. On the other hand, as a population ages, the potential support ratio tends to fall, meaning there are fewer potential workers to support the elderly. Retirement planning is based primarily on the calculation of the elderly dependency ratio and potential support ratio. It also needs to analyze the total **dependency ratio**, the ratio of combined youth population (ages 0-14) and the elderly population (ages 65+) per 100 people of working age (ages 15-64). Because a 'high total dependency ratio' indicates that the working-age population and the general economy face a greater burden to support and provide social services to youth and elderly persons, who are often economically dependent (<https://www.cia.gov/library/publications/the-world-factbook/>). Retirement planning is necessary for aged people who have retired from work and are no longer in a position to participate in any productive activity to generate income. Traditionally, especially in agrarian social system old people would comfortably stay in their family and families had also the ability to bear their financial and other burden. In developing countries mainly for economic reasons, families have lost their ability to bear the responsibilities of senior members after retirement to death. So planning for the old people of the country constitutes important elements of national human resources planning. In Bangladesh, as in 2015, the old age dependency ratio (65+ per 20-64) was a 9.1 ratio. The old age dependency rate (65 + per 20-64) of Bangladesh increased from 6.1 ratio in 1966 to 9.1 ratio in 2015 growing at an average annual rate of 0.82 % (<https://knoema.com/atlas/Bangladesh/topics/DemoFigureics/Dependency-Ratios>). The picture is shown in the following Figure and table:

Figure 4 Ratio of population aged 65+ per 100 populations 20-64 years

Table 12 Ratio of population aged 65+ per 100 populations 20-64 years

Year	Value	Change, %
2015	9.1	-0.43 %
2014	9.1	0.11 %
2013	9.1	0.60 %
2012	9.0	0.89 %
2011	9.0	1.11 %
2010	8.9	0.41 %
2009	8.8	0.73 %
2008	8.8	1.03 %
2007	8.7	1.30 %
2006	8.6	1.54 %
2005	8.4	0.95 %
2004	8.4	

According to another calculation, the Bangladeshi old age dependency ratio was 10.9 ratio in 2015, the single year for which the data is available at the moment (<https://knoema.com/atlas/Bangladesh/topics/DemoFigureics>). However, the elderly dependency rate in Bangladesh according to above statistics is high and is in increasing trend. That is, the pressure on the government to support the elderly is increasing.

To understand the gravity of the situation, the potential support ratio demands consideration. In 2015, the potential support ratio (20-64 per 65+) for Bangladesh was 11 ratios. The potential support ratio (20-64 per 65+) of Bangladesh fell gradually from 15.7 ratio in 1970 to 11 ratio in 2015(<https://knoema.com/atlas/Bangladesh/topics/DemoFigureics>)the decreasing ratio indicates that there are fewer people to support the elderly people. Figure 4 and Table -12 depict facts in this regard.

Figure 5 Ratio of population aged 20-64 per population 65+ years in Bangladesh (Potential Support Ratio)

Table 13 Ratio of population aged 20-64 per population 65+ years in Bangladesh (Potential Support Ratio).

Date	Value	Change, %
2015	11.0	-2.24 %
2010	11.3	-4.85 %
2005	11.9	-5.35 %
2000	12.5	-7.53 %
1995	13.5	-3.38 %
1990	14.0	0.30 %
1985	14.0	3.67 %
1980	13.5	-4.45 %
1975	14.1	-10.34 %
1970	15.7	-6.22 %
1965	16.8	-0.99 %
1960	16.9	

If the 40 million unemployed workforces in Bangladesh are considered in the calculation of the potential support ratio, the horrifying actual situation becomes evident. It reflects that the families and societies in Bangladesh have alarmingly losing their capacity to support the elderly and vulnerability of the elderly people is increasing day by day with acceleration. Thus, the traditional social capital used to ensure holistic comfort for the elderly in Bangladesh is also under a rapid destruction process.

In these circumstances Bangladesh needs to make urgently elderly people involving the society and the family. Currently the government has social safety net program to support extremely poor elderly people specially women is very insignificant compared to the gravity of the present situation.

2. Concluding Remarks

The phenomenon of national human resource planning as the well as functional relationship between NHRP and development, still to get due attention as they deserve in Bangladesh, like many other developing countries. Currently more than 100 million people in Bangladesh work abroad and earning huge volume of remittances for the country, but the country could not make a proper plan considering them as the main force of development change. The population pyramid and the status of different dependency ratios as well as potential support ratio analysis fail to contribute to the formulation of development planning. The issue of dynamic equilibrium is under threat due to the absence of proper

population planning, education planning, employment planning and elderly dependency planning with due emphasis on hard and soft sides of planning and on harmonious balance among them. The study reveals the fact that the National Human Resource is not functional in Bangladesh. The prevalent realities in the fields of population, education, employment and elderly services indicate a conceptual obscurity about NHRP on the part of the governance. There are imbalances internally in all the elements of the cycle of events and an imbalanced relationship among the elements themselves. All these together represent a serious disruption in the cycle of events corresponding to the vulnerable state of dynamic equilibrium in society and underdevelopment syndrome.

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